

Proposed names for the GAIA instruments/fields/detectors

L Lindegren, 1998 June 23 (SAG_LL_019)
Rev 1, 1998 July 5 (SAG_LL_019_1)
Rev 2, 1998 July 6 (SAG_LL_019_2)

A hierarchic list of proposed names is given below
(abbreviations/acronyms in round brackets)
[old names in square brackets]

Astrometric Instruments (Astro) [ASTRO]
Astro-1 [ASTRO-1]: the first (preceding) Astrometric Instrument
Astrometric Sky Mapper (ASM) [PSM]
ASM0 (detect bright stars) } NOTE: detailed
ASM1 [PSM1] (detect/position) } functions are
ASM2 [PSM2] (confirm/rate, backup) } not reflected
ASM3 [PSM3] (confirm/rate) } in the names
Astrometric Field (AF)
AF01
...
AF17
Broad Band Photometer (BBP) [FSM]
BBP1
BBP2
BBP3
BBP4
Astro-2 [ASTRO-2]: the second (following) Astrometric Instrument
(same division as Astro-1)
Spectrometric Instrument (Spectro) [APT]
Spectrometric Sky Mapper (SSM)
Narrow Band Photometer (NBP) [Photometer] (see COMMENT)
NBP1
...
NBPN where n=7 (TBC)
Radial Velocity Spectrometer (RVS) [ARVI]

COMMENT

Note in particular the following changes:

1. Astro instead of ASTRO (since it is not an acronym)
2. Spectro instead of APT or APT/ARVI etc
3. RVS instead of ARVI
4. "Sky Mapper" is reserved for the detectors used to detect objects entering a field (ASM in Astro, SSM in Spectro), and the old attributes Preceding/Following are replaced by functional descriptions.

To distinguish between (e.g.) BBP1 in the two Astro instruments one would have to say "BBP1 in Astro-2", "Astro-2/BBP1" or similar, but not "following BBP1" (which could be confusing).

SAG is considering the possibility to use low-resolution spectrometer(s) for photometry in Spectro, replacing the filters. In this case NBP may be replaced by LRS (Low Resolution Spectrometer), possibly in turn consisting of two spectrometers (LRS1 and LRS2) optimised for different wavelength regions.

Changes from Rev 1 -> Rev 2:
BASM -> ASM0
MASM1 -> ASM1 (etc)
